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- PU: Public (*on-line platform)
- PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
- RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
- CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

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1 Executive Summary

Dissemination activities are considered of primary importance for the BigDataStack project Consortium since the impact of the project can only be meaningful if the achieved results are widely communicated to the public.

The target groups for the dissemination activities are divided into several equally important categories, including experts and key stakeholders in the area of:

- Big data organizations and initiatives (BDVA, Open Source Initiative, think tanks, NGOs, etc.)
- Entrepreneurs, ICT SMEs & Start-ups
- Standardisation bodies
- Open source projects and initiatives
- Academia and research
- Big Data PPP projects and other pertinent H2020 initiatives (including ICT14 & ICT15)
- General public

The dissemination activities and all the material developed so far are evenly directed towards all these categories, implementing in every individual case various communication tools and channels.

This deliverable provides a description of the initial set of materials that has been produced so far to define and promote the project's identity.

Section 3 provides information on the project branding and logo.

Online material is presented in **Section 4**, including the description of the website and the social media channels that are used not only to provide updates and news, but also as a tool to promote event activities.

Section 5 describes the BigDataStack monitoring system set-up to collect analytics for each of the dissemination channels and related Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

Finally, **Section 6** reports the templates that have been developed to deliver and present project results and the collaboration tools adopted by the Consortium as project development space and document management system.

2 Introduction

Every European or nationally funded Research and Innovation project or support action project, with specific milestones and outputs to achieve, faces formidable challenges when it comes to designing and executing an effective communication and dissemination strategy. The concept of a communication strategy should immediately trigger the elements portrayed in Figure 1, which are all parts of the dissemination strategy that BigDataStack will adopt.

In recent years, the terminology of “disseminating your project results” for many consortia does not go beyond the interpretation of having the project results published in a limited number of scientific publications and perhaps a lukewarm presence at a related event to which no quantifiable or measurable results were ever listed to guarantee the impact necessary.

Indeed, for BigDataStack, the dissemination of the project results is a crucial factor that is pursued through a number of initiatives and dissemination channels and tools aiming at informing the communities of the different stakeholders identified about its project results. From the onset, the project wishes to actively utilise its pilot end-users to demonstrate the efficacy of BigDataStack. This is a good channel for credibly introducing what the results of BigDataStack will offer in terms of value-proposition, through the most important actors- the end-users!

Figure 1 – Communication & dissemination evolving around BigDataStack

By M6, Work Package 7 will define a first internal version for **the Communication and Collaboration Plan (D7.4)**. D7.4 will provide a description of the stakeholder groups that BigDataStack project targets and lay out communication plans for reaching out to these communities. This deliverable (D7.1) provides an overview of the branded dissemination and communication materials created during the first two months of the project that will be used both at events and online in M1-12. The plan will map the identified assets of the project

against the stakeholder group that will utilise these assets.

3 Branding and logo

A revised logo was introduced before the project began to suitably brand the project. The first way to “communicate” the project is through identification with the project logo. In BigDataStack, the logo is represented by a graphical item and a pay-off text underneath so the reader can easily recognise the context the project is working in. Various formats of the logo will be created where needed for use in different contexts (web, media, printed material).

Figure 2 – BigDataStack project's logo and pay-off in different applications

4 Communications channels and materials

4.1.1 Website

The Project's website was published at the end of February 2018. It is intended to be a dynamic communication one stop shop at the service of the entire Consortium, that is all partners shall contribute with texts, documents and images to its deployment. The web site showcases the project, with the institutional information like goals, objectives, news and an overview of the benefits of BigDataStack to each stakeholder group, how the groups can engage with BigDataStack and related events.

BigDataStack.eu is an integrated and versatile web platform aimed at building a community of users and disseminating the achieved scientific results. The website will be dynamic and will frequently change during project lifetime. It will be the channel to showcase concrete results and help to drive awareness of BigDataStack solutions, helping users in all sectors to understand and evaluate the benefits of project technologies.

BigDataStack.eu has been developed using Drupal 7¹, which is an open source Content Management System (CMS). This platform was chosen since it has standard features that are functional and easy to use, such as content authoring, reliable performance, and excellent security. The Drupal Platform (written in PHP language) was found to be extremely flexible and modular. Finally, the Drupal platform is a well-suited base to develop a GDPR-compliant platform. Data are stored on a relational database management system (RDBMS) MySQL. Drupal documentation and source code are available on www.drupal.org². The specific BigDataStack.eu implementation includes a customised graphical theme which is stored on the Trust-IT servers, located on the Amazon Cloud (EC2), in Ireland.

During this first phase of the project, the web platform sections have been populated with project related information, regarding the project vision, scientific domains have been addressed and a short description of the use cases, together with relevant content organized according to format and topic: news items and publications provided.

Specifically, the following menu is active:

- **About:** providing general information on the project and in particular:
 - **Project overview** and which objectives the project will address
 - **Consortium:** who's behind the initiative
 - **Key pillars** offered by the project
- **Use cases:** a section to showcase a description of them and how the project outcomes will be validated and challenged by three commercial use cases
- **News & Events:** listing the news and the project related events where BigDataStack partners are involved
- **European Open Source Initiative:** this page provides an overview of how BigDataStack will create valuable open source artefacts and maximizing impact for the European Open Source Initiative
- **Publications:** while the page is not active at the moment, it will contain the project documents relevant for external stakeholders, i.e. scientific articles, press releases, presentations and papers

The website will require a continuous improvement to the indexation with **Search Engine Optimisation** (SEO) on-page techniques in order to make the content on the portal more appealing to search engines. This implies:

- XML side-map

¹ <https://www.drupal.org/docs/7>

² <https://www.drupal.org/docs/7>

- meta title, meta descriptions and meta keywords modules on the backend of the website to improve snippets of the most relevant content
- set-up the Google Search Console, a free service that enables to monitor site's performance in Google Search, to ensure that Google can crawl the site, and to test the validity and performance of a given page.

Concerning the SEO assessment, two metrics have been adopted to monitor branding and performances of the portals. Google Keyword Planner Tool was used to find the most relevant keywords that will drive ongoing web traffic and conversions on BigDataStack.eu. A set of 20 keywords was selected and will be monitored and updated during all the project lifecycle. To better analyse keyword performance, weekly monitoring of two parameters will be performed:

- **Position Tracking** help to monitoring the different portal's keyword rankings in order to measure the success of a search engine optimisation activity. Higher positions for target keywords indicate a successful strategy, and lower positions indicate that the competition is outperforming
- **Brand monitoring:** this metric helps to understand how the BigDataStack brand is perceived and allows to understand where brand is mentioned and, discover which channels are being used by competitors. This can help to understand how users perceive the brand, as well as where the services are being mentioned on the web.

The data will be weekly extracted by Trust-IT via SEMrush³, a tool specialised in SEO analytics.

Figure 3 – BigDataStack Landing page

4.1.1.1 Procedures implemented to support GDPR compliance

Different procedures and specific functionalities have been implemented and are continuously maintained to ensure compliance to the General Data Protection Regulation

³ <https://www.semrush.com/>

(GDPR), according to the Rights, Accountability and Governance requirements that are reported in Table 1.

Table 1 – GDPR: rights, accountability and governance

GDPR main points	Typical Drupal website installation
The right to be informed	Privacy notice webpage
The right of access	Usually all user data are accessible after login
The right to rectification	Usually all data are editable by the user
The right to erasure	It's possible to delete user account
The right to restrict processing	It's possible to disable user account, data will be still visible but can't be changed anymore
The right to data portability	It's possible to provide data export in CSV format
The right to object	In the privacy notice: * You must inform individuals of their right to object "at the point of first communication" and in your privacy notice. * This must be "explicitly brought to the attention of the data subject and shall be presented clearly and separately from any other information".
Rights related to automated decision making and profiling	Usually no automated processing of personal data on Drupal
Accountability and governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Implement appropriate technical and organisational measures that ensure and demonstrate that you comply. This may include internal data protection policies such as staff training, internal audits of processing activities, and reviews of internal HR policies. * Maintain relevant documentation on processing activities. * Where appropriate, appoint a data protection officer. * Implement measures that meet the principles of data protection by design and data protection by default. Measures could include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data minimisation; Pseudonymisation; Transparency; * Allowing individuals to monitor processing; and * Creating and improving security features on an ongoing basis. * Use data protection impact assessments where appropriate.
Breach notification	You only have to notify the relevant supervisory authority of a breach where it is likely to result in a risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals.

For more detailed information on our use of these technologies, please see our Privacy

Policy⁴.

In case of data breach, a notification will be sent within 72 hours to Commission de la protection de la vie Privée, Rue de la Presse, 35, 1000 Brussels.

4.1.2 Social media Channels

Social media activities have enabled the creation of selected channels which will include active contributions to specific Social Media such as Twitter, LinkedIn and contributions to discussion groups, direct messaging and leveraging current connections within the consortium with the aim of building a loyal support base.

Two branded social media platforms have been set up in early January 2018 and populated: Twitter⁵ ([@BigDataStackEU](https://twitter.com/BigDataStackEU)) and [LinkedIn](https://www.linkedin.com/in/bigdatastack-project-81508b155/)⁶.

Figure 4 – BigDataStack Twitter and LinkedIn accounts

Twitter

Twitter is mainly used to provide brief real-time updates and news, but also as a tool to promote event activities.

The BigDataStack Twitter account is intended to reach a broad audience and to send out specifically tailored messages to different stakeholders on particular occasions.

We report some example of Tweets produced so far targeting the general public audience.

⁴ <http://www.bigdatastack.eu/privacy-policy>

⁵ <https://twitter.com/bigdatastackeu?lang=en>

⁶ <https://www.linkedin.com/in/bigdatastack-project-81508b155/>

Table 2 – Examples of Targeted Tweets

Tweet	Stakeholder Target
	<p>General Public</p>
	<p>Research Institutions & Open Source Community</p>

LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a business- and employment-oriented social networking service that is mainly used for professional networking. The objective is to use LinkedIn not only to provide updates and news but to create also discussion groups and leveraging current connections within the consortium with the aim of building a loyal support base.

Figure 5 – Example of LinkedIn Post

4.1.3 Factsheet

The factsheet emphasizes the key points of the projects including an overall description, a summary of the main objectives, information on how BigDataStack project is addressing scientific and technical challenges, as well as outlines and benefits to each stakeholder group. The PDF version can be downloaded from the website [here](#)

Figure 6 – Factsheet (front)

Figure 7 – Factsheet (back)

4.1.4 MS PowerPoint presentation

The Slidedeck provides a concise presentation of the project with a description of the expected results, the concept & the approach, the offerings for the different stakeholders, general information about the Initiative and contact references. The PDF version can be downloaded from the website [here](#)

Figure 8 – MS PowerPoint presentation

4.1.5 News

A news piece announcing the project kick-off has been published in early January. The article provides the essentials of the projects, an overall description of the objectives, the list of partners behind the initiatives and a focus on the three use cases that will be developed during the project.

The full article can be found at the following [link](#). Published also on Twitter and LinkedIn.

5 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) & Monitoring

5.1.1 Monitoring set up & KPIs consolidation

More than ever funded projects are required to provide measurable indicators of the impact of research outputs, because research funders increasingly demand measurable valorisation of research. It is therefore fundamental that means to measure the impact of dissemination are set up and woven into the dissemination strategy from its start. BigDataStack will set up the monitoring system for each of the dissemination channels and pinpoint specific KPIs and a suitable timeline for collecting the statistics. Section 5.1.2. provides an example of the Flash report that is produced on a weekly basis to monitor the KPIs.

5.1.2 Flash Report

The Flash Report is intended as a tool for monitoring on a weekly basis the evolution of the project's online presence. Briefly, we monitor the growth of the community through LinkedIn and twitter followers and the registered users of the official website. Moreover, by tracking

the periodic publication of content on the various social platforms deployed and by linking this information to the growth of the community and other valuable data, practical considerations about the impact and outreach of the communication of the project can be inferred.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
1													
2													
3					01/01	08/01	15/01	22/01	29/01	05/02	12/02	19/02	26/02
4	Community KPIs				W1	W2	W3	W4	W5	W5	W6	W7	W10
5	Community KPI	Target EoP (M36)	Missing	Achieved so far									
6	Tweets	//	//	//									
7	Twitter followers	//	//	//									
8	Twitter Impressio	//	//	//									
9	Twitter Engagem	//	//	//									
10	LinkedIN posts	//	//	//									
11	LinkedIN connec	//	//	//									
12	Slideshare uploa	//	//	//									
13	Slideshare viewe	//	//	//									
14	Youtube Video	//	//	//									
15	Newsletters	//	//	//									
16	Press Release	//	//	//									
17	WebSite												
18	Monthly Web content	//	//	//									
19	Registered users	//	//	0									
20	Unique visitors [#]	//	//	0									
21	Session [#]	//	//	0									
22	Average session [s]	//	//	00:00									
23	Bounce Rate	//	//	%									
24													
25	Community DB	0	0	0									

Figure 9 – Flash report template

6 Templates and collaborative tools

6.1.1 Templates

Two templates have been created, one for the PPT presentation that all partners may use for their presentations and activities (within the project and in other events where BigDataStack will be presented) and one for the Word document (acting as a placeholder for project deliverables), both indicating the EC logo and disclaimer and privacy overview.

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Figure 10 – Deliverable template

Bigdatastack.eu
@bigdatastackeu

BigDataStack
Holistic stack for big data applications and operations

Title

Type of event, place, date

Name Surname
Role, Organization
email address

Co-funded by the European Commission
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Figure 11 – Sliddeck template

6.1.2 OwnCloud

An OwnCloud repository has been activated and set up to provide the Consortium with a shared, secure and easy to use cloud service file repository. Accounts have been created for all project participants.

6.1.3 Wiki

A Wiki platform⁷ has been activated and set up to provide the Consortium with a flexible collaboration platform used to keep information related to meeting minutes, agendas, open topics, links to the OwnCloud repository, etc. The wiki is based on TWiki, an open source wiki and application platform with an extensible plugin architecture. TWiki is a cgi-bin script written in Perl.

6.1.4 Mailing list

Several mailing lists have been created to facilitate working groups communication with different recipient groups, at management level (general assembly, Monthly Management Report), work package level and technical level (architecture, use cases).

7 Conclusions

This deliverable reports the initial set of materials that have been produced in the first two months of the project to define and promote BigDataStack project's visual identity and the initiation of communication project materials. It includes the creation of a project logo, a project factsheet, the project's official web site, first iteration, social media accounts and templates for the official documents to be developed within the project.

All these activities, together with the printed material (flyers, posters and pop-up banners) that will be produced in the upcoming months, form the basis of a series of communication and engagement initiatives covering key areas in the project, and will be produced during the organisation and participation to several events and workshops during the year. Specific and tailored communication strategies and materials will be developed for each event, in order to target the audience in the most effective way, to help grow the community and engage with all the stakeholders.

M6-12 will see a number of deliverables produced which the project may capitalise from the content perspective and replicate this onto the communication materials delivered.

M12-14 will see the usage and adaptation of content from these documents to create newly branded materials for both online and offline communication. As related projects have also initiated during 2018, BigDataStack will use these months to create valid cooperation activities with other BIG DATA PPP initiatives specifically the projects funded under the EC H2020 ICT '14 and ICT '15 where the consortium has introduced a targeted strategy for

⁷ <http://wiki.bigdatastack.eu>

understanding what cooperation may be carried out with them, this will be described in the D7.4 Communication and collaboration plan.